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Are Team Member Contributions Correlated with Cohesion and Performance
Behaviors for Software Engineering Students?

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Software engineering is an activity quite depending of team work nowadays. In the last decades, this aspect has raised the interest of software engineering educators. In academic contexts, team work can be affected when team members (students) are not contributing equally. In other contexts, team member contributions have been found correlated with the cohesion of teams, the last one being a good predictor of performance. Although some researches have studied the performance of student teams, they mostly have been focused on measures related with outcomes rather than behaviors. This work presents a study on the relations between these variables, with a sample of 95 Cuban software engineering students performing in teams. The student teams were exposed to the “*Stick-Together*” approach, a proposal grounded on the Input Mediators Outcomes Input (IMOI) model. The aim of this approach is to improve team cohesion which leads to better team performance behaviors. In this approach self and peer assessment of team member contribution is considered in order to avoid the free-ride problem. This paper describes the way in which students’ contribution is related to cohesion and performance behaviors in order to better understand the relationships between these variables in regard to the adoption of this approach.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Skills, Discipline-specific Teaching & Learning and Curriculum Development

Keywords: team work, member contribution, cohesion, performance behaviors, software engineering education

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INTRODUCTION

In modern software development teamwork is a critical success factor. Developers have to work together performing independent task to produce quality products in a continuous changing technological environment. During this process they have to adapt in an agile way for reaching the team's goals, experimenting complex relationships while interacting under project restrictions of time, budget, and others. Thus, to prepare software engineers to effectively perform on teams is an important matter nowadays.

Some studies in economics reveal that peers stop cooperating when they believe they are being exploited by a free-rider [1]. A free-rider is an individual with a conscious decision to withhold effort when the ability to contribute is present. Similarly, in academic contexts students express a dislike for team work because of increased pressure when team members are not performing equally [2]. Some authors state that free-riding is one of the most important cause of student dissatisfaction within team work [3], [4]. Balance on team member contributions is critical in software teams with members who have expertise in different areas (core development, GUI development, system architecture, testing, etc.) [5].

Team member contributions have been found correlated with the cohesion of teams [6]. The last one has being found strongly correlated with performance when this is measured as behaviors [7]. These three variables were included in our *Stick-Together* approach, a proposal grounded on the Input Mediators Outcomes Input (IMOI) model [8], [9]. Several studies were conducted to observe if this proposal leads to improve team cohesion pursuing the aim of obtaining better team performance behaviors [10][11]. In *Stick-Together* approach self and peer assessment of team member contributions are considered in order to avoid the free-ride problem. In this paper we focus on describing the way in which students' contribution was related to the cohesion and performance behaviors during the series of experiments conducted.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 1 describes the context of the study, the method of intervention and the variables. Section 2 refers to the results observed. Section 3 discusses some limitations of the study and Section 4 concludes the paper.

1 METHODOLOGY

Ninety five software engineering students from the University of Holguin participated in the study. It was conducted over five study cases during one year till February 2018. They were performing in twenty two teams of 3-6 members, all using agile methodologies to develop software.

The main objective in this series of experiments was to observe if the *Stick-Together* approach was effective to make teams more cohesive leading to improve team performance behaviors. Fig. 1 shows an overview of this approach, which consists of three phases, and is conducted over periods of ten to twelve weeks.

Fig. 1. Our *Stick-Together* approach

Team member contributions were evaluated on five areas, according to low, medium and high levels of team performance behaviors, by means of the questionnaire proposed by [6]. This instrument uses a behaviorally anchored rating scale to measure team member contributions in five areas. The areas include 1. contributing to the team's work, 2. interacting with team mates, 3. keeping the team on track, 4. expecting quality and 5. having relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSAs).

Team performance is seen as behaviors related to the tasks and team learning. Team performance is usually measured with indicators for effectiveness and efficiency. However, [1] differentiated between performance behaviors and performance outcomes. Team performance behaviors are actions relevant to achieving goals, whereas outcomes are the consequences or results of performance behaviors. In this study we assume the criteria of [12] who define team learning as the "activities carried out by team members through which a team obtains and processes data that allow it to adapt and improve". Performance on task is assessed following the criteria of the same author as the degree in which the team satisfies client needs and expectations. Team performance behaviors as a variable is then studied in these two aspects: "Team Performance Behaviors on Task" and "Team Learning".

Team cohesion is thought of in two very different ways, as proposed by [13]: the social attachment within the team and the team's connection to the project itself (calling these social "S" and task "T"); and at two levels of granularity: at the individual level and for the team as a whole (calling these Individual Attractions to the Group (ATG) and Group Integration (GI)). The combination of these two dimensions and two levels result in measuring four aspects of team cohesion:

- GI-T: The team's attachment to the task
- GI-S: The team's social connection
- ATG-T: Individual attachment to the task
- ATG-S: Individual connection to the team

It is beyond the scope of this study to examine the effectiveness of the *Stick-Together* application. Some works have previously discussed that matter [10], [11]. In this paper we

focus on the way in which students' contribution is related to cohesion and performance behaviors before and after the application of the *Stick-Together* approach. In particular, we examine the following research questions:

RQ1: Are team member contributions correlated with team performance behaviors on task?

RQ2: Are team member contributions correlated with team learning?

RQ3: Are team member contributions correlated with team cohesion?

2 FINDINGS

The analysis of the research data was performed with the SPSS 20.0 software package. Shapiro-Wilk test confirmed non-normal distribution for all variables. All the tables in this section show the Spearman correlation coefficient and p-values. For each analysis are shown the values before (marked in tables with sub-indices 1) and after (marked in tables with sub-indices 2) the application of the *Stick-Together* approach.

The coefficients of the significant correlations (99% confidence) are marked with '***', i.e. they have a significance level of 0.01, meaning that the error probability is less than 1%. The coefficients of correlation confirming positive relationships between the factors at a confidence level of 95% are marked with '**', that is, they have a significance level of 0.05, and the error probability is <5%.

A first analysis did not indicate any correlation between team member contribution and performance behaviors before the application of *Stick-Together*. However, it was found that team member contribution positively correlates with the final team learning ($r=0,358^{**}$, $p=0,000$). A specific analysis for each area is presented in *Table 1*. It shows the values for each area of team member contribution and team performance behaviors, this last variable presented as team performance behaviors on task (TPBT) and team learning (TL).

Table 1. Correlation between team member contributions and team performance behaviors

Team Member Contributions' areas		TPBT ₁	TPBT ₂	TL ₁	TL ₂
Contributing to the team's work	<i>r</i>	0,105	0,079	0,072	0,021
	<i>p</i>	0,312	0,445	0,485	0,837
Interacting with teammates	<i>r</i>	0,058	0,113	0,015	0,015
	<i>p</i>	0,579	0,275	0,887	0,884
Keeping the team on track	<i>r</i>	-0,057	0,008	-0,004	0,014
	<i>p</i>	0,585	0,937	0,971	0,894
Expecting quality	<i>r</i>	-0,192	0,222*	-0,189	0,559**
	<i>p</i>	0,063	0,031	0,067	0,000

Having relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSAs)	<i>r</i>	-0,076	0,238*	-0,139	0,247*
	<i>p</i>	0,462	0,020	0,180	0,016

* $p < 0.05$.

** $p < 0.01$.

As can be seen in the table above, not any team member contributions' area was correlated with performance behaviors before the application of *Stick-Together*. Nevertheless after that, *Expecting quality* and *Having relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSAs)* were found correlated with team performance behaviours on task ($r=0,222^*$, $p=0,031$ for *Expecting quality*; $r=0,238^*$, $p=0,020$ for *KSAs*) and team learning ($r=0,559^{**}$, $p=0,000$ for *Expecting quality*; $r=0,247^*$, $p=0,016$ for *KSAs*).

A first analysis concerning cohesion indicated correlation between this variable and performance behaviors in both moments, before ($r=-0,459^{**}$, $p=0,000$) and after ($r=-0,218^*$, $p=0,034$) the application of *Stick-Together*. Table 2 shows the values for the analysis of each area of team member contribution and cohesion. Before the application of *Stick-Together* none relationships were found. However after the application, a positive correlation was found between cohesion and the areas *Expecting quality* and *Having relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSAs)*.

Table 2. Correlation between team member contributions and cohesion

Team Member Contributions' areas		Cohesion ₁	Cohesion ₂
Contributing to the team's work	<i>r</i>	0,116	0,017
	<i>p</i>	0,264	0,868
Interacting with teammates	<i>r</i>	0,092	0,034
	<i>p</i>	0,378	0,740
Keeping the team on track	<i>r</i>	0,028	0,022
	<i>p</i>	0,786	0,831
Expecting quality	<i>r</i>	0,002	0,676**
	<i>p</i>	0,986	0,000
Having relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSAs)	<i>r</i>	0,010	0,288**
	<i>p</i>	0,925	0,005

* $p < 0.05$.

** $p < 0.01$.

A second analysis over cohesion and team member contributions is shown in *Table 3*. Here are displayed the values for each area of team member contribution and each of the four cohesion's aspects.

Table 3. Correlation between team member contributions' areas and cohesion's aspects for both dimensions

Team Member Contributions' areas		Cohesion's aspects							
		GI-T ₁	GI-T ₂	GI-S ₁	GI-S ₂	ATG-T ₁	ATG-T ₂	ATG-S ₁	ATG-S ₂
Contributing to the team's work	<i>r</i>	0,087	-0,128	0,010	0,027	0,152	-0,123	0,089	0,162
	<i>p</i>	0,403	0,216	0,9240	0,799	0,141	0,237	0,393	0,118
Interacting with teammates	<i>r</i>	0,047	-0,153	0,003	0,000	0,097	-0,093	0,091	0,165
	<i>p</i>	0,650	0,138	0,978	1,000	0,350	0,372	0,378	0,110
Keeping the team on track	<i>r</i>	0,025	-0,172	-0,030	0,140	-0,067	-0,172	0,077	0,013
	<i>p</i>	0,813	0,096	0,774	0,177	0,521	0,096	0,461	0,900
Expecting quality	<i>r</i>	-0,150	0,220*	-0,160	0,429**	0,126	0,412**	0,146	0,504**
	<i>p</i>	0,147	0,032	0,122	0,000	0,225	0,000	0,158	0,000
Having relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSAs)	<i>r</i>	-0,068	0,015	-0,149	0,106	0,049	0,139	0,108	0,374**
	<i>p</i>	0,514	0,885	0,150	0,305	0,641	0,180	0,299	0,000

* $p < 0.05$.

** $p < 0.01$.

The values in *Table 3* show no correlations before the application of *Stick-Together*. However after the application, *Expecting quality* was correlated with all the aspects of cohesion ($r=0,220^*$, $p=0,032$ for GI-T; $r=0,429^{**}$, $p=0,000$ for GI-S; $r=0,412^{**}$, $p=0,000$ for ATG-T; $r=0,504^{**}$, $p=0,000$ for ATG-S). The area *Having relevant Knowledge, Skills, and Abilities (KSAs)* was also found correlated with *Individual connection to the team* ($r=0,374^{**}$, $p=0,000$).

3 LIMITATIONS

The validity of the results presented here is limited by the fact that it uses a questionnaire-based approach and peer evaluation research. Students were asked to assess their own behaviors and their teammates', and that might go against the reality as some students could rate themselves with the highest scores or mark others with unfair criteria. However, in order to avoid this, they were informed that this assessment would not influence their grades. On the other hand, the correlations found might also be explained by other variables involved in the *Stick-Together* approach, such as the level of conflicts, task characteristics or personality

traits [14]. In addition, characteristics of the context such as students differences with regard to computers and other resources required for the development of their projects, limitation of information sources, among others factors, could affect the way in which they contribute and perceive the others' work.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a study on the correlational relationships exhibited by software engineering student teams between team member contributions and the cohesion and performance behaviors during a series of experiments along one year. The findings show that *Expecting quality* and *Having relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs)*, are important areas of team member contribution for cohesion and performance behaviors of software engineering students teams. Contrary to the results found by [6], our findings didn't confirm the importance of *Contributing to the team's work*, *Interacting with teammates* and *Keeping the team on track* for cohesion. However, some correlations between areas could explain undirected effects on team cohesion and performance behaviors. For instance, *Having relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs)* was found correlated with *Contributing to the team's work* ($r=0,319^{**}$, $p=0,002$), *Interacting with teammates* ($r=0,351^{**}$, $p=0,000$) and *Expecting quality* ($r=0,213^*$, $p=0,038$). This finding is consistent with the reports by the same authors in the study aforementioned. They explain that team members with strong relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities are more likely to contribute highly to the team's work than students who lack the necessary skills to contribute. In the same way it has been stated that team members who are highly skilled in areas related to the team's work also display better social skills and contribute more to team discussions [15]. Thus, while *Expecting quality* and *Having relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs)* would be the most important areas in our study, we shouldn't ignore surfacing effects of *Contributing to the team's work* and *Interacting with teammates* areas. Moreover, comparing the results before and after the application of *Stick-Together*, it seems that this approach has an influence on the students' expectations about team's success and production of high-quality work, besides the role of knowledge, skills and abilities required for getting excellent results. Thus, further studies will explore other involved variables and their influences enabling a better clarification.

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